

D7.2: Website launch

[WP7 – Communication and dissemination]

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Abstract

This report describes the structure of the SIENNA website, the visual identity of the project, and the process used to develop content for the SIENNA website. It describes the website's role in SIENNA communications, serving as the main point of contact for the project, with a structure that allows the consortium to tailor communication for different target audiences as the project progresses.

This report also describes the first steps towards developing a communications and dissemination strategy for SIENNA. It precedes the communication strategy and plan, which will be delivered by 31 December, 2017. Hence, some of the content of this report is to be considered interim in relation to the SIENNA Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3).

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	02 Oct, 2017	First Draft	Review	Contributors
V0.2	02 Nov, 2017	Second Draft	Quality assurance	Reviewers
V1.0	19 Dec, 2017	Final version	Review comments	Coordinator, H2020

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Plan	<p>This report outlines the SIENNA visual identity and approaches to readability and SEO.</p> <p>The action plan included in this report will be carried over to the D7.3 report.</p>

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Executive summary

The SIENNA website is available at www.sienna-project.eu. The website is part of the project's communication strategy and the main point of contact for all target audiences. It is also a tool for branding, in terms of key messages and visual identity. Launching the website is a key achievement for the SIENNA project. As such, the timing was planned to coincide with the launch of the project to ensure a point-of-contact exists when partners start working on the project. It was also timed to be delivered before issuing the first SIENNA press release (D7.1) to ensure a supporting resource with information about the project was available.

SIENNA communications aim to be accessible and available. For the website, this is addressed in three ways: 1) technical aids, design and testing, 2) choice of language, and 3) a strategy for visual communication.

The website has four landing pages, allowing for tailored communications as the project starts producing results. The start page is the main point of contact for the SIENNA project, describing the SIENNA approach to stakeholder informed ethics for new technologies. The site also features three second level landing pages, one per technology area.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action (SIENNA full project proposal)
PMC	Project Management Committee
RSS	Rich Rite Summary (see glossary for explanation)
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
URL	Address on World Wide Web
WP	Work Package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
InfoGlue	Content Management System (CMS) used by Uppsala University.
Landing page	Main point of entry (start page) for specific audiences.
RSS	Web feed that allows users to access content updates in a format that is standardised and in a format that can be read by computers.
Wireframes	Page schematic or screen blueprint (i.e. a visual guide that represents the framework or 'skeleton' of a website).
Visual identity	Graphical identify and other visual elements (colour scheme, fonts).

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Web presence is important for the SIENNA project for several reasons. A project website serves as the main point of contact. The SIENNA website was launched on September 29, 2017 (Friday) in order to be up and running for the official start date on October 1, 2017 (Sunday), and subsequent press-release on October 19, 2017¹. The site was delivered ahead of time to ensure the project had a point of contact at its inception. The website is designed to reflect the project structure, present the technology areas, partners and the people involved in SIENNA. As the project starts delivering results, the structure will be adapted to reflect this (i.e., adding a section for publications, calendar for SIENNA events, etc.).

1.2 Objectives

The objective of this report is to describe the function and thinking behind the SIENNA website, its current state, the purpose of establishing this web presence, and outline the plan for maintaining, updating, developing and sustaining the website and its content.

1.3 Structure of the report

This report outlines the methodology used in the development of the first version of the SIENNA website. It explains the structure of the website, the visual identity the website establishes, domain and website hosting and the website's role in SIENNA communications. This report is on the critical path to Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3) and includes a preliminary action plan that will be included in the D7.3 deliverable.

1.4 Scope and limitations

This report describes the first steps in developing a visual identity and communications strategy for SIENNA.

2. Process for developing the SIENNA website

The development of the SIENNA website is an iterative process that draws from lessons learned from developing a website for the Innovative Medicines Initiative project PREFER (Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle), www.imi-prefer.eu, which was launched in October 2016 and uses the same InfoGlue template for external projects provided by Uppsala University².

This template was adapted to fit the SIENNA visual identity, which was also developed based on a model developed in PREFER. The website also draws from experiences structuring and developing content for other websites under the Uppsala University domain, for example www.crb.uu.se and www.ethicsblog.crb.uu.se.

The website development process had ten steps:

1. Developing a design dummy/wireframe to be discussed with the coordinator (UT), followed by the PMC.
2. Adapting the template provided by Uppsala University based on the design dummy.
3. Developing preliminary website structure with wireframes.
4. Populating structure with content from the SIENNA description of action (DoA)
5. Presenting beta version to the PMC for review and input to the process.

¹ Fernow et al., *D7.1 Press Release (SIENNA)*.

² Fernow, "D1.1 Website Launch (PREFER)".

6. Further development of website structure and content, followed by discussion and approval by the PMC.
7. Content was developed further and reviewed by the SIENNA coordinator, deputy coordinator, WP leads and other consortium members.
8. All consortium members were asked (on two occasions) to provide biographies, send photos and sign permissions to publish. Consent to publish biographies was presumed by provision and/or approval of biography for the SIENNA website.
9. The website went live at 10 AM on 29 September, 2017.
10. Consortium members were informed and encouraged to continue reviewing, and updating their information as needed.

After launching the website, Uppsala University assumes responsibility for hosting, maintaining and updating the website and domain.

3. SIENNA website structure

The first version of the SIENNA website has one top-level landing page (see glossary of terms) for the project (www.sienna-project.eu), and three second-level landing pages, one per technology. This allows us to tailor communications for stakeholders in different areas as the project progresses and starts producing results. This structure is reflected in the top navigation, which includes the followings tabs:

Top navigation (tabs)	Left navigation	Content description
About SIENNA	Introductory text describing the SIENNA project, including acknowledgement and list of partners.	
	Project structure	Text describing six work streams, or “work packages” supported by a management team at the University of Twente and a communications team at Uppsala University. Page includes contact information of WP leaders.
	Theory and methodology	WP1 specific page with short text describing tasks. WP leader listed for contact and more information. This page will be updated to include all WP members.
	Ethical Impact Assessment	Description of SIENNA approach to Ethical Impact Assessment.
	Stakeholders, Experts and citizens	Description of how we intend to collect input from these groups.
	SIENNA proposals	WP5 specific page with short text describing tasks. WP leader listed for contact and more information. This page will be updated to include all WP members.
	Adapting SIENNA results	WP6 specific page with short text describing tasks. WP leader

Top navigation (tabs)	Left navigation	Content description
		listed for contact and more information. This page will be updated to include all WP members. Blurbs pointing visitors to this part of the website will be added as more content is developed.
	Contact SIENNA	Contact information for coordinator, deputy coordinator and communications.
Genomics	WP2 specific landing page with image and short blurb (see figure 4) and introductory text.	
	About Genetics and Genomics	A short text explaining the technology area.
	Ethical, legal and social analysis	List of steps involved in the analysis. This bullet point list is mirrored on corresponding pages for other technologies. This text will be developed as the project progresses.
	People	In the first (launch) version of this website, this page lists the partners involved as defined in the proposal. The WP leader's photo and bio is listed for contact and more information. This page will be developed to include a list of WP members.
Enhancement	WP3 specific landing page with image and short blurb (see figure 5) and introductory text.	
	About Human Enhancement	A short text explaining the technology area.
	Ethical, legal and social analysis	List of steps involved in the analysis and short introductory text tailored to the Enhancement work package. A bullet point list mirrors lists on corresponding pages for other technologies. This text will be developed as the project progresses.
	People	In the first (launch) version of this website, this page lists the partners involved as defined in the proposal. The WP leader's photo and bio is listed for contact and more information. This page will be developed to include a list of WP members.

Top navigation (tabs)	Left navigation	Content description
AI & Robotics	WP4 specific landing page with image and short blurb (see figure 6) and introductory text.	
	About AI & Robotics	A short text explaining the technology area.
	Ethical, legal and social analysis	List of steps involved in the analysis. This bullet point list is mirrored on corresponding pages for other technologies. This text will be developed as the project progresses.
	People	In the first (launch) version of this website, this page lists the partners involved as defined in the proposal. The WP leader's photo and bio is listed for contact and more information. This page will be developed to include a list of WP members.
News	Subpage with SIENNA news in other languages added on October 30.	List of news and RSS feed. This part of the website will be re-structured and developed with social media RSS-feeds and used to list and track press-coverage of the SIENNA project.
Partners	List of partners	Partner descriptions with logos.
	People	Bios, photos and contact information in alphabetical order (first name) following coordinator and deputy coordinator.
Planned development of website structure (suggestions to be discussed at a later stage)		
Publications	List of publications generated either manually in the form of static lists, or dynamic feed from the DiVA portal ³ at Uppsala University (to be discussed). This section should also ideally list information about authorship (as outlined in the CA) and data management policy in SIENNA.	
Deliverables	Section presenting SIENNA deliverables and outputs.	
Events	Calendar function and event reports.	
Media coverage	RSS-feeds from social media and publicity tracking.	

Table 3: SIENNA website structure

The structure of the SIENNA website will evolve as the project progresses. It is worth noting that it is technically possible to add more language versions to the website. The CMS supports versions in Swedish, English, German, French, Spanish, Danish, Chinese and Arabic. However, the text-to-speech function (Readspeaker) does not support all languages.

³ <http://www.diva-portal.org/>

3.1 About landing pages

The SIENNA project landing page is the main point of contact. This page is designed to convey the message that this project is focused on technology, ethics and human rights in three domains: human genomics, human enhancement and human machine interactions i.e., AI & Robotics. These three areas are made visible in the top navigation bar, links in the text and in blurbs at the bottom of the text. These blurbs are repeated elsewhere on the website, helping visitors to navigate between technology areas, and from text about the project to specific technology areas.

The SIENNA approach: Stakeholder informed ethics

SIENNA (Stakeholder-Informed Ethics for New technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impAct) will develop ethical protocols and codes for [human genomics](#), [human enhancement](#) and [AI & robotics](#).

Figure 1: Landing page, www.sienna-project.eu

The content and visuals in the technology specific blurbs mirror the respective landing page main visual and content. Graphics have been selected to create a harmonised colour scheme (see section 4 on visual identity).

Figure 2: Technology specific blurbs

Apart from technology-specific blurbs, the landing page also includes a news-feed, blurbs pointing to sub-sections of the “About” tab, and specific “calls to action” that can be used to highlight current developments in the project. As the project progresses, this space will be used to display a calendar for project events, and possibly also RSS-feeds to connect other (future) SIENNA channels (i.e., social media feeds) to the main website.

The screenshot shows a landing page design with a purple background. On the left is a 'News' section with a white background, containing a news item about ethical and legal aspects of new technologies dated 2017-08-31, and a 'More news' link. To the right are two columns of blurbs. The first blurb is titled 'Ethical impact of technology' and features an image of a green circuit board with a 'BIG DATA' tag and a key labeled 'Technology Security'. The text describes a model for ethical impact assessment. The second blurb is titled 'SIENNA's contribution' and features an image of orange and grey 3D cubes. The text describes the development of ethical codes for human genomics, human enhancement, AI & robotics. Both blurbs include a 'Read about assessments' or 'Developing our proposals' link.

Two purple call-to-action blurbs are shown. The first is titled 'CITIZENS & EXPERTS' and contains the text: 'Our work is informed by citizens, experts and stakeholders in human genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction: find out how!'. The second is titled 'SIENNA METHODOLOGY' and contains the text: 'The SIENNA project started on October 1 2017. In the first seven months, we build the methodological foundation. Find out more!'. Both blurbs have a white arrow pointing to the right.

Figure 3: Other landing page blurbs and design items

The screenshot shows the SIENNA website. The header features the 'sienna.' logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'About SIENNA', 'Genomics', 'Enhancement', 'AI & Robotics', 'News', and 'Partners'. The 'Genomics' section is active, showing a sidebar with 'Genomics' selected and sub-links for 'About Genetics and Genomics', 'Ethical, legal and & social analysis', and 'People'. The main content area has a dark background with a green DNA helix. It includes a 'Human Genetics & Genomics' section with a sub-header 'Ethical, legal and social analysis' and 'Who are we?'. The text states: 'Genetics and Genomics research can help us understand the molecular causes of disease. Technologies to sequence or edit DNA can become powerful tools to diagnose and treat diseases, yet they also raise important ethical, legal and social issues.' Below this is a section titled 'Genetics and Genomics: Impact on society' with a sub-header 'New and improved technologies for genetic and genomic research are slowly making their way from research to patients and consumers. This raises ethical, legal and social questions for both individuals and society.' and a paragraph: 'New technologies such as next generation sequencing make it possible to test individuals and screen large populations more efficiently. Genetic testing for screening'.

Figure 4: Second-level landing page: Genomics <http://www.sienna-project.eu/genomics/>

Figure 5: Second-level landing page: Enhancement <http://www.sienna-project.eu/enhancement/>

Artificial Intelligence and Robotics: Impact on society

More and more people have interactions with robots, smart devices, intelligent software, prosthetics and implants. They are used in industry, the education system, health care, our homes, the entertainment industry and military applications. The potential benefits are abundant. However, there are considerable ethical and legal challenges.

In order for machines to perform in an intelligent and autonomous way, they need to collect data. What do we expect from intelligent software in terms of morality? Are we

Figure 6: Second-level landing page: AI and Robotics <http://www.sienna-project.eu/robotics/>

4. Visual identity

SIENNA has a clear technology, ethics and human rights focus. Our aim is to support this with our choices of graphics on the website (and elsewhere). We use a mix of graphical and photographic images. When depicting people, we aim to select a range of images that are representative of the people of the world, taking care to represent a wide range of people in terms of genders, ethnicity and other characteristics.

4.1 Using graphics and photographic images: SIENNA policy

The SIENNA consortium comprises people and organisations. As far as possible, we will display partner logos and portrait photos of researchers to show who and how roles are filled in SIENNA. However, we will take due care and use appropriate consent mechanisms when publishing pictures and videos that can identify individuals. The SIENNA project uses graphics that are in the public domain, mainly from www.pixabay.com. As a rule, we will not use images that are watermarked (with or without © marking) in digital communication. For portrait photos given to us by members of the consortium in SIENNA communications, we assume that the consortium member has the right to share it with us. When available, we include the photographer's names in metadata of the image. In cases where a photo is clearly taken by a professional photographer, our policy is to ask whether we are free to use the image before using it in digital or printed media.

The SIENNA website is hosted by Uppsala University and, as such, falls under Swedish personal data legislation, requiring permission to publish any video or photo that can identify an individual. The SIENNA project will collect such permissions from individual members of the consortium and store them electronically on the project SharePoint information repository hosted by the University of

Twente. Copies of these permissions will also be stored locally at Uppsala University by the project's communications team. In preparation for the launch of the website, a preliminary visual identity was developed for SIENNA. This will be developed further and described in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3). The aim is to make SIENNA:

- Visible as an entity.
- Identifiable in the European project context.
- Uniform in external and internal communications.

In connection with the website launch, this visual identity has been adapted for PowerPoint templates and deliverable reports. Other templates will be developed by WP7 in the first phase of the project (and defined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan).

Tools	Guidelines	Background/motivation
Colour scheme	Orange (#FF7F00) Purple (#46008C) Black Grey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contrast for screen • Colours are neutral and not connected to specific technology area or scientific field (compare blue = medicine, red = danger).
Logo	Font: Agency FB, regular Orange & black "landscape" format Adaptable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the proposal phase, a logo was developed for the project. Its continued use has been approved by the PMC. • The PMC has decided to allow the logo to be adapted for different technology areas (adding text underneath). This will be developed further and described in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3).
Web design	Builds on Uppsala University's template for non-UU websites. Orange (#FF7F00) Purple (#46008C) Black Grey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contrasting colours • Tested for accessibility • Contemporary look • Easy to re-create in print
PowerPoint template	White background, Black text, grey and green.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mirrors web-design • Accessible to colour blind people.
Fonts	To be finalised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available • Readable
Other print materials	To be finalised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posters, booklets and flyers will mirror the SIENNA PowerPoint template and web design.

Table 4: SIENNA visual identity

5. Domain and website hosting

Uppsala University is hosting the SIENNA website in the InfoGlue content management system. Uppsala University’s domain master also registers the domain. At the time of writing this, the only cost attached is related to web-design for adapting the generic template to fit the SIENNA project’s visual identity. However, there will likely be costs attached to hosting the project website after the project ends. For this reason, we recommend earmarking a part of the communications budget as a contingency for future costs, and to ensure that the web presence can be sustained after the project ends (after March 2021).

5.1 Training, technical support and disaster recovery

The InfoGlue helpdesk is manned Monday to Friday between 09:00-16:00 and can be contacted via e-mail (info glue-support@uadm.uu.se) or via link provided in the top navigation of the CMS. Uppsala University also provides training for editors and website owners, and a web resource for support (<http://support.webb.uu.se/>).

InfoGlue servers are kept in two separate locations at Uppsala University. Backups are incrementally saved every night using an enterprise-grade backup system. Database content backups are saved for 8 days. Disaster recovery is handled on a per-case base. Requests can be made either by phone or e-mail, contacting Uppsala University’s Servicedesk. The Servicedesk can be contacted weekdays 08:00-21:00 and on weekends 14:00-17:30.

6. Website role in SIENNA communications

The SIENNA website will be the main point of contact for almost all audiences for SIENNA communications (defined and described in the Communication and Dissemination Plan). It is also a tool for branding, in terms of both key messages and visual identity.

At the beginning of the project, the website also plays an important part in project internal communications, allowing consortium members to familiarise themselves with the project, and other people working on the project. For this reason, delivery before the project kick-off benefits the consortium as it makes SIENNA visible and tangible in terms of internal communications.

The website is part of the communication goal “recognition and identification” as outlined in the SIENNA proposal, represented by graphical identity and acknowledgements (see table 5 below). This will be described in further detail in the SIENNA Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3).

Recognition and identification	Graphical/visual identity	Logo and graphical identity, including guidelines for use and instructions on how to acknowledge SIENNA and the European Commission.
	Acknowledgements	All communications will acknowledge SIENNA and the Commission according to H2020 and SIENNA guidelines (outlined in D7.3).

Table 5: Visual identity’s contribution to making SIENNA recognisable

7. Accessibility and availability

SIENNA aims for available and accessible communications. This means that accessibility and availability always comes before the visual communication in all channels, including web. This website design has been tested according to accessibility standards and that the design is optimised for mobile and other devices. Uppsala University provides a text-to speech function (ReadSpeaker), making the website accessible for dyslexics and the visually impaired. The website is also tested for colour contrast, increasing accessibility for the colour blind.

The SIENNA website should welcome all SIENNA target audiences. This statement has consequences for both language and visual communication (see section 4. Visual identity). The first version of the website was developed based on audiences outlined in the proposal text. The purpose, objectives, audiences and key messages for SIENNA communications will be described in D7.3 The SIENNA dissemination and communication plan (available in December, 2017) and website content will be adjusted accordingly.

Language and readability: Adapting content for lay audiences risks over-simplifying complex issues. However, in a multi-disciplinary project, text for lay audiences are worth striving for, even for academic audiences. We also acknowledge the fact that our audiences are not all native (or fluent) English speakers. To help ensure we are understood, we use readability testing, aiming for a grade average of 14 using either the Flesch-Kincaid⁴ and/or the SMOG grading formula (Simple Measure of Gobbledygook)⁵. Another reason to aim for low readability grades is to improve SEO.

With partners (and associate partners) from Europe, Asia, America and Africa, SIENNA acknowledges the need for translating communications to local languages, vocabularies and nomenclatures. In our official communications, we have opted for British English spelling.

8. Measuring outreach

The SIENNA website uses a Google Analytics tracking ID (UA-107301828-1). An account to track website traffic was established on September 29, 2017. The SIENNA communications team at Uppsala University will track website traffic and report on it as part of WP7 monitoring. Key performance indicators for the website will be outlined in the SIENNA Communication and dissemination plan (D7.3).

⁴ Kincaid et al., *Derivation of New Readability Formulas (Automated Readability Index, Fog Count, and Flesch Reading Ease Formula) for Navy Enlisted Personnel. Research Branch Report 8-75.*

⁵ McLaughlin, "SMOG Grading: A New Readability Formula".

9. Action plan

Action plans for the website for 2018 onwards will be outlined in Deliverable 7.3 and/or the WP7 work plan maintained by Uppsala University. Below a tentative action plan for the continued development of the SIENNA website.

Timing	Communication intent	Communication channel	Communication lead	Other resources	Status
Oct 2017	Updates	Website	Josepine Fernow	All consortium members	Ongoing
Oct 19 2017	Press release	Global release	Laurens van der Velde		Completed
Oct 19 2017	Web news (multiplying press release)	SIENNA website	Josepine Fernow		Completed
Oct 2017	Collect permission to publish	SharePoint server	Josepine Fernow	All consortium members	Completed
Nov 2017	Discuss tentative audiences and objectives for SIENNA communications	Suggestions and review procedures	Josepine Fernow	All consortium members	Completed
Q1-Q4 2018	Discuss further development of SIENNA website	Meeting	Josepine Fernow		Planned

Table 6: Preliminary action plan for Q3, 2017

10. Risks and risk mitigation

Risks and suggested mitigations for the SIENNA website will be outlined in Deliverable 7.3 and/or the WP7 work plan maintained by Uppsala University. Below a tentative list of risks and risk mitigations identified in the process of developing the website.

Risk to the SIENNA project website	Level	Mitigation
UU ceases development of the InfoGlue platform	Medium	Uppsala University will procure and develop a new content management system (CMS) for web. The process starts in 2018. This means it will cease development of the InfoGlue platform where the SIENNA project website is currently hosted. This means no new functionality will be added to the website. Should this be a problem for SIENNA, it will be possible to migrate the content to the new UU CMS (which will be likely be available in 2020). Support for the existing website will remain.
Key personnel leave the project	Low	A team of two people at Uppsala University, allowing knowledge transfer, will maintain the SIENNA website.
Failure to drive and attract traffic to the SIENNA website	Low	The SIENNA website has a generic URL. This requires taking SEO measures when developing content for the website (i.e., using keywords in headings, synonyms in text, adapting text to reach low readability scores etcetera). Mitigating this risk also requires using other media to drive traffic to the website. A plan for this will be developed by the UU communications team.

Table 7: Website related risks (and mitigation)

11. Conclusion

The SIENNA website is the main point of contact for the project. This means it is necessary to provide contact information for researchers involved in the project.

The website needs to serve many disparate audiences, ranging from individuals, policy-makers, media, other stakeholders and experts in genomics, human enhancement, AI & robotics. Visitors have different languages, educational backgrounds, gender and abilities. This requires accessible, available and readable communications, taking care to cater and adjust to a range of visitors in our visual communications.

The website launch is the first step in executing SIENNA communications. The content of this report will feed into the SIENNA Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.3). As the project progresses, and as statistics on its use become available, the website will be reviewed and developed further, both in terms of structure and content.

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